

PREPARING GRAPE JUICE FOR THE WINTER

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Abstract. *Medicine can be delicious. This is the phrase that comes to mind when it comes to natural grape juice. Made at home, completely devoid of harmful chemical additives, this drink has been used in folk medicine since ancient times as a general tonic. Fortunately, you can still prepare this delicious medicine by hand today. It just takes a little effort. This drink is effective in the treatment of many diseases. Easily digestible sugar, vitamins, micro and macro elements, organic acids in the composition of berries make grapes a real storehouse of nutrients, and its juice - a concentrated health benefit.*

Keywords: *grapes, grape processing, juice, benefits of grapes, storage of grapes.*

ЗАГОТОВКА ВИНОГРАДНОГО СОКА НА ЗИМУ

Аннотация. *Лекарство может быть вкусным. Это фраза, которая приходит на ум, когда речь заходит о натуральном виноградном соке. Сделанный в домашних условиях, полностью лишенный вредных химических добавок, этот напиток издревле используется в народной медицине как общеукрепляющее средство. К счастью, сегодня вы все еще можете приготовить это вкусное лекарство вручную. Просто нужно немного усилий. Этот напиток эффективен при лечении многих заболеваний. Легкоусвояемый сахар, витамины, микро- и макроэлементы, органические кислоты в составе ягод делают виноград настоящим кладом полезных веществ, а его сок – концентрированной пользой для здоровья.*

Ключевые слова: *виноград, переработка винограда, сок, польза винограда, хранение винограда.*

INTRODUCTION

Due to the significant content of vitamins, glucose and fructose, the drink has a tonic and antioxidant effect on the body. It is effective for the prevention of cardiovascular diseases, has a mild laxative effect, and also lowers cholesterol levels. Juice is useful for neurosis and anemia. Also, its unique chemical composition has a positive effect on brain function.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

It is not recommended to introduce this drink into the children's diet before the age of two. In general, it is indicated for use in children with insufficient body weight and weak immunity. In addition, grape juice is a good natural energy booster that can increase the mental and physical activity of a child.

RESULTS

The main argument in favor of a drink prepared at home is its naturalness. By preparing it at home, any housewife can guarantee that this drink is completely free of any chemical additives or dyes and stabilizers harmful to the body.

But freshly squeezed juice is a perishable product. Oxidative processes in it begin almost instantly. And sterilization and boiling destroy many useful substances. At the same time, the process of preparing a drink for the winter is very laborious.

DISCUSSION

But, despite all these disadvantages, compared to homemade, a drink in a bag is one big drawback. The most important thing to think about when purchasing it is how many preservatives, flavor enhancers and flavorings are dangerous for the body.

In addition, such drinks often contain a very high percentage of sugar, which is also not very healthy. Well, the packaging itself leaves much to be desired. To preserve the beneficial properties of natural juice, glass containers are best suited, since the paper still has microcracks.

Of course, this drink can be made from any white or black variety. But practitioners recommend giving preference to the best wine varieties that have optimal sugar content / acidity, as well as good juice characteristics.

CONCLUSIONS

To prepare a tasty and healthy drink at home, it will take a lot of time, because without the use of technological progress, this process becomes quite laborious.

Preparation of a drink at home is carried out in several stages:

- The bunches of grapes are washed and the berries are separated from the branches, breaking them into a large basin.
- Ready berries are gently crushed with hands, carefully, trying not to miss a single berry.
- The resulting liquid with pulp is filtered through a fine sieve into a saucepan.
- Using a ladle, the product is poured into prepared clean bottles, filling them approximately 3/4 (sterilizing the bottles is not necessary).
- A towel is placed at the bottom of the pan, bottles are placed and covered with lids without twisting.
- Pour water into the pan at the level with the liquid in the bottles.
- Sterilize for 20 minutes from the moment of boiling, after which the lids are twisted.

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